

Studies on the Effects of Dicyandiamide on the Acid Corrosion of Some Aluminium Alloys

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The effects of dicyandiamide on the acid corrosion of some aluminium alloys, in 1N hydrochloric acid, has been investigated. From the investigations it has been found that aluminium alloy of 50S variety is more corrosion resistant than the other two types under the same conditions. Dicyandiamide retards the corrosion of the alloys at a critical concentration of 0.4M above which it acts in a catalytic manner and increases corrosion rate.

ACID corrosion of aluminium alloys and the effects of organic additives on them have been studied by many workers¹⁻¹⁰. Unni and Ramachar have studied the corrosion properties of different aluminium-magnesium alloys in the presence of a number of non-reducible organic amines as additives⁵⁻⁸. Experimental data relating to the acid corrosion of aluminium alloys in the presence of reducible compounds are still lacking. Preliminary investigations were carried out in this laboratory on the inhibitive action of dicyandiamide on the acid corrosion of pure aluminium¹¹. Dicyandiamide and related compounds show good inhibitive properties on the acid corrosion of different metals¹²⁻¹⁵. This paper reports the effect of dicyandiamide on different varieties of aluminium alloys of technological interest in 1N HCl acid.

Experimental

Three varieties of aluminium alloys (1) 1S, (2) 50S, (3) B51S, manufactured by Indian Aluminium Company were used for the present investigation for their wide spread use in industry. The nominal composition of which are as follows :

- (1) Alloy 1S (Al-99.3%, Si-0.3%) ;
- (2) Alloy 50S (Si-0.5%, Mg-0.6%, rest Aluminium) ;
- (3) Alloy B51S (Si-1%, Mg-0.9%, rest Aluminium).

The first variety was in the form of sheet whereas other two varieties were obtained in the form of rods, these were cut to pieces and their surface area were determined carefully. The edges and corners were kept coated with an acid resistant resin (Araldite). The surfaces were abraded with different grades of emery papers (150, 320, 450, 600) and finally polished against 4/0 polishing paper. They were finally, thoroughly washed with water, dried and used for the experiments. The surface areas

exposed for corrosion studies were 1.0 cm² for 1S alloy, 0.2 cm² for 50S and B51S alloys.

Acid :

A. R. qualities of hydrochloric acid (sp. gr. 1.18) was used for preparing 1N HCl. Dicyandiamide was L. R. variety (B.D.H., U. K.) and was used after recrystallization from alcohol. 150-200 ml of acid inhibitor solutions were taken and the metal coupons were dipped for 5 hrs.

All measurements were done using a thermostat at 25±0.2°. The corrosion rates were expressed in mg/hr/surface area.

The weight loss experiments were carried out a number of times and reproducible data were recorded (±1%). The abnormalities at 0.4M concentration were checked up.

Results and Discussion

The corrosion rates of the alloys investigated in 1N hydrochloric acid in absence and in presence of dicyandiamide has been tabulated in the Table. In

TABLE—CORROSION DATA OF ALUMINIUM ALLOYS IN 1N HYDROCHLORIC ACID AT 25°C IN PRESENCE OF DICYANDIAMIDE

Inhibitor Concentration (Molar)	Alloy 1S mg cm ⁻² h ⁻¹	Alloy 50S mg cm ⁻² h ⁻¹	Alloy B51S mg cm ⁻² h ⁻¹
0.0	0.210	0.030	0.260
0.1	0.110	0.050	0.330
0.2	0.088	0.040	0.320
0.4	0.050	0.020	0.210
0.5	0.290	0.100	0.450
Inhibition efficiency at 0.4M of Dicyandiamide			
	1S	50S	B51S
I%	67.25	45.74	19.60

pure acid alloy 50S is found to have a better corrosion resistance than the other two varieties. This difference is possibly due to the difference in magnesium and silicon contents in the alloys. Dicyandiamide appears to be a better inhibitor for 1S variety but for the other two alloys it affords no protection and rather corrosion rate is accelerated due to the addition of a small amount of the organic compound. However, the factor of critical concentration seems to be involved here as all the alloys investigated show a decrease in corrosion in the acid at a particular concentration of 0.4 M of the organic compound. It seems that the difference in the corrosion behaviours of all the three alloys is due to difference in magnesium and silicon content. Frery¹⁶ stated that addition of magnesium improves corrosion resistance of aluminium alloys to most chemicals. However, Kemkhadze and Balezin¹⁷ pointed out that reducible inhibitors can act upon a metal in two opposing ways. They can either inhibit or accelerate the process of dissolution and at a given concentration of the inhibitor, one or the other tendency is predominant. According to them, the rate of reduction of reducible groups, and thus, the stimulation of corrosion, increase with increased inhibitor, concentration. The falling off in inhibitive power of dicyandiamide may be due to the reduction of the reducible-cyano group to 'imino' or -amino product.

Conclusion :

It seems that dicyandiamide which is a quite effective inhibitor for 1S variety and for others effective only at a critical concentration of 0.4 M of inhibitor. Above this concentration inhibition efficiency decreases.

The mechanism of inhibition is by adsorption of the compound over metal surface through third nitrogen atom and due to planarity of the molecule,

the probability of multicentred adsorption along with other N-atoms is also possible.

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